

Theoretical study of H-bond complexes of nitrous acid with fluoro-methanes

H. C. Tandon^{a*} and Mudassir M. Husain^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Venkateswara College, Dhaura Kuan, New Delhi-110 021, India

E-mail : hctwave@yahoo.co.in

^bPhysics Section, Department of Applied Sciences & Humanities, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Jamia Millia Islamia (a Central University), New Delhi-110 025, India

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Abstract : The equilibrium geometries, binding energies and vibrational spectra of CH₃F, CH₂F₂ and CHF₃, nitrous acid and their C-F...HONO-bonded complex have been investigated with the standard 6-31G** basis set *ab initio* calculation performed at the Möller-Plesset second-order (MP2) level. In all these complexes, a strong C-F...HONO, halogen-hydrogen bond is formed. The strength of the hydrogen-bonded complexes show a decreasing trend as one go from CH₃F to CHF₃ with both *cis*- and *trans*-form of nitrous acid. Large hydrogen-bond distances are predicted in *cis*-HONO complex with fluoro-methanes as compare to *trans*-HONO complex. Furthermore, C-F bond decrease in HONO (*trans*) complexes has been observed, whereas in HONO (*cis*) complex C-F bond increase is observed. This is an unusual observation. The red shift in all the complexes of nitrous acid with fluoro-methanes correlated well with C-F bond lengthening.

Keywords : Nitrous acid, fluoro-methanes hydrogen bond complex, blue shift, Möller-Plesset second-order (MP2).

Introduction

Noncovalent interactions play an important role in many fields of chemistry and biochemistry as they determine the structures and properties of liquids, molecular crystals, and biological molecules¹⁻⁴. The hydrogen bond is of particular significance among possible noncovalent interactions⁵⁻⁸. Due to its crucial importance, a large number of studies on the hydrogen bond phenomenon have been reported over the years including both theoretical calculations and experimental results⁹⁻¹⁵. Energetics and spectroscopic attributes of weak C-F...H hydrogen bonds have been widely discussed in recent literature¹⁶. A primary reason for the overwhelming interest to this subtle type of attractive molecular interaction is due to a notion that, collectively, such weak forces could be an important determining factor for stability of many important biomolecular structures¹⁷⁻²¹. One of the intriguing spectroscopic features of such hydrogen bonds, 1 : 1 complex of haloalkanes as hydrogen bond donor and water, ethers and small carbonyl compounds as acceptors, is the spectral blue-shifting of the stretching fundamental of the donor C-H group with concomitant diminution of its infrared absorption intensity²²⁻²⁴. Thus, the two universal

spectroscopic features of classical hydrogen bonds (X-H...Y) red shifting and IR intensity enhancement of the donor X-H stretching vibration are reversed in the former cases and the traits have also been predicted by electronic structure calculations²⁵⁻³⁰.

In the present work, we performed a detailed examination of binding energies, electronic structure, stretching frequency, charge distribution, geometry optimization for all the structures including monomers and complexes were carried out by using the second order perturbation theory (MP2) in conjunction with the standard 6-31G** basis set. This level of theory has proved to be quite good in evaluating geometric and energetic parameters for infrared H-bond complexes. The geometries were fully optimized without symmetry constraint. Harmonic vibrational frequencies were subsequently performed at the same level to identify the true equilibrium structures.

The selection of nitrous acid molecule and its interaction with fluoro-methanes has a paramount importance in the field of atmospheric chemistry which influenced us to study such reactions. Nitrous acid, one of the smallest molecule plays a major role in atmospheric chemistry and exhibits *cis-trans* conformational equilibrium. The stud-

ies of nitrous acid complexes with various bases β -HONO in low temperature matrices have shown that these complexes, in which OH group acts as a proton donor have comparable strength with the corresponding complexes of hydrogen halides, β -HX with the same bases^{32,33}. The classification of the structure and stability of the hydrogen bonded complexes of nitrous acid with various atmospheric bases is very important for atmospheric chemistry. The *cis-trans* isomerism of nitrous acid was the first reported instance of an infrared stereochemical reaction^{34,35}.

It is an unstable molecule in the vapour phase and occurs in the complex equilibrium with the products of its decomposition. We, in our previous work, carried out the hydrogen bond complexation of nitrous acid (*cis/trans*) with B_2O_2 and C_2N_2 molecular systems³⁶. Many workers, earlier, carried out theoretical and experimental work in the field of hydrogen bonded complexes with various molecules viz. CH_4 , C_2H_2 , Co and N_2 ^{37,38}. Since the strength of these hydrogen bonds, is expected to be small, the steric and electronic effects could play a very different role from that in standard hydrogen bonds.

As a model of more complex systems, the interaction between nitrous acid and the different methyl flourides has been chosen for the present work. As we know, nitrous acid (HONO) exists in *cis*- and *trans*-forms, hence its interactions with CH_3F , CH_2F_2 and CHF_3 has been studied to determine the influence of flourination in the hydrogen bond of the electronegativity of the atoms attached to the carbon.

Computational details :

Geometry optimizations were performed with the Hyperchem 7.52 program³¹. The geometries were optimized by using Polak-Ribiere (conjugate gradient) method, which is fast and accurate computing algorithm, keeping r.m.s. gradient at 0.01 kcal/Å mol and convergence limit at 0.01. In all the cases global minima is established.

Results and discussion

Nitrous acid and flourmethanes :

The geometrical parameters and net atomic changes of nitrous acid (*cis* and *trans*), flourmethanes and their corresponding complexes are shown in Figs. 1–10. The electrostatic potential maps of these complexes are given

in Figs. 11–16. The contour diagrams in the scans are self-explanatory, showing the global minima during complexation. It can be seen from Fig. 1 that the calculated bond length and bond angles of *cis*-HONO and *trans*-HONO in free state are in good agreement with the avail-

The numbers in parentheses are experimental values taken from Ref. 29. Bond lengths are in Å units

Fig. 1

able experimental values. As mentioned earlier, these results are obtained by using 6-31G** standard basis set at Möller-Plesset, second order correlation function (MP2). We tried with other basis sets, 6-311+G** and 6.311++G**, but showed marginal improvement in the molecular geometries toward experimental results and moreover, the chemistry of H-bond remained same in all basis sets. Hence, we report the results with only 6-31G** basis set. In present case the H-bond complexation between HONO and flourmethanes have been reported. The *cis*-HONO monomer is found to be stable by 1.35 kcal mol⁻¹ than *trans*-HONO monomer (see Table 1). Similarly the geometries and net atomic charges of monomers of flourmethanes (CH_3F , CH_2F_2 and CHF_3) are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The calculated bond length and bond angles are in close agreement with available experimental results.

$CH_3F \cdots HONO$ (*cis/trans*) complexes :

The structural parameters and net atomic charges of these H-bonded complexes are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. It

Table 1. Energetics and electronic parameters at MP2/6-31G** of monomers of nitrous acid and fluoro-methanes

Systems/Parameter	CH ₃ F	CH ₂ F ₂	CHF ₃	HONO (<i>cis</i>)	HONO (<i>trans</i>)
B.E. (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-87248.77	-149284.41	-211328.50	-128417.42	-128416.07
μ (Debye)	1.981 (1.715)	2.052 (1.718)	1.710 (1.424)	1.608 (1.561)	2.619 (2.651)
HOMO (eV)	-14.1900	-14.2743	-15.9832	-12.6618	-12.2100
LUMO (eV)	6.8168	6.9035	7.2823	3.1846	3.3501
ΔE (eV)	21.0068	21.1778	23.2655	15.8464	15.5601

The numbers in brackets are the experimental values taken from Ref. 41.

Net atomic charges on atoms

Fig. 2

The numbers in parentheses are experimental values taken from Ref. 40. Bond lengths are in Å units

Fig. 3

can be seen from the results that the C-H and C-F bonds in (CH₃F), on complexation are shortened by 0.002 Å and 0.0034 Å respectively compared to their monomers.

Net atomic charges on atoms

Fig. 4

The selected energetic and electronic parameters of nitrous acid and fluoro-methanes in free state and in H-bonded complexes are given in Tables 1 and 2. The C-F...H bond distance is predicted to be 1.9439 Å. Furthermore, the O-H bond of HONO (*cis*) is elongated by 0.04 Å on complexation, similar to the observations made by Turi and Dammenberg³⁹ while showing H-bonded complexes in HCN-H₂O, C₂H₂...H₂O systems (see Fig. 5).

Similarly, the complexation of CH₃F...HONO (*trans*) system, the H-bond distance is found to be 1.9110 Å, less by 0.0329 Å as compared to *cis*-complex.

Along the same line of argument, the net atomic charges are also altered significantly on those atoms which are involved in complexation for both *cis*-HONO and *trans*-HONO with respect to the molecules in free states. The net change in the atomic charges on H-atom (involved in H-bond) are 0.23e, 0.20e and 0.31e, 0.17e for *cis* and *trans* complexes respectively (Fig. 6).

Table 2. Selected energetics and electronic parameters at MP2/6-31G** of nitrous acid and fluoromethanes H-bond complexes

Systems	Binding energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Dipole moment (μ) (Debye)	HOMO (eV)	LUMO (eV)	ΔE (eV)
CH ₃ F+					
HONO (<i>cis</i>)	-215671.20	3.9000	-12.1649	3.6393	15.8042
HONO (<i>trans</i>)	-215671.02	4.3280	-11.8285	3.7013	15.5298
CH ₂ F ₂ +					
HONO (<i>cis</i>)	-277705.38	4.0520	-12.2512	3.5706	15.8218
HONO (<i>trans</i>)	-277704.31	5.3430	-11.7754	3.7759	15.5513
CHF ₃ +					
HONO (<i>cis</i>)	-339749.28	0.6475	-12.7967	3.0317	15.8284
HONO (<i>trans</i>)	-339747.18	4.4650	-11.9503	3.5996	15.5499
H-Bond energy					
CH ₃ F-HONO (<i>cis</i>)	-7.00				
CH ₃ F-HONO (<i>trans</i>)	-6.18				
CH ₂ F ₂ -HONO (<i>cis</i>)	-3.55				
CH ₂ F ₂ -HONO (<i>trans</i>)	-3.83				
CHF ₃ -HONO (<i>cis</i>)	-3.06				
CHF ₃ -HONO (<i>trans</i>)	-2.61				

Bond lengths are in Å units

Fig. 5

Net atomic charges on atoms

Fig. 6

CH₂F₂...HONO (cis/trans) complexes :

The geometrical and net atomic charges of these complexes are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. One can see that the C-H and C-F bonds (during complexation) are shortened by 0.0002 Å and 0.0120 Å respectively as compare to the

monomers. The C-F...H bond distances are 2.0747 Å and 2.0423 Å respectively for *cis* and *trans* complexes. The C-F bond distances on complexation with *cis*- and *trans*-HONO are predicted to be increased by 0.0120 Å

Bond lengths are in Å units

Fig. 7

CH₂F₂/HONO (*cis/trans*) complex

Net atomic charges on atoms

Fig. 8

and 0.0162 Å with respect to CH₂F₂ monomer.

In addition to the elongation and shortening of the bonds during complexation, the change in the net atomic charges on the atoms involved in the H-bonding also takes place.

CHF₃...HONO (*cis/trans*) complexes :

The optimized geometric parameters and net atomic charges on H-bond complexes are shown in Figs. 10 and 11 respectively. One can see from the computed value

CHF₃-HONO (*cis/trans*) complex

Bond lengths are in Å units

Fig. 9

CHF₃-HONO (*cis/trans*) complex

Net atomic charges on atoms

Fig. 10

Fig. 11. ESP map of $\text{CH}_3\text{F}\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*cis*).

Fig. 12. ESP map of $\text{CH}_3\text{F}\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*trans*).

Fig. 13. ESP map of $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*cis*).

Fig. 14. ESP map of $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*trans*).

Fig. 15. ESP map of $\text{CHF}_3\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*cis*).

Fig. 16. ESP map of $\text{CHF}_3\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*trans*).

that the C-H and C-F bonds, on complexation, are shortened by 0.001 Å and 0.141 Å respectively to its monomers. The largest shrinking of C-F bond is predicted as compared to the bonds in CH_3F and CH_2F_2 complexes. It may be due to large shifting of the shared electrons towards the three fluorine atoms in CHF_3 . The C-F...H bond lengths are 2.1387 Å and 2.1482 Å in $\text{CHF}_3\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*cis*) and $\text{CHF}_3\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*trans*) respectively. Similarly, the net atomic charges on the atoms involved in H-bonding are also predicted to be quite significant. This is in agreement with the experimental and high level theoretical work carried out previously.

Now, to summarize the results, on the basis of the geometrical and electronic changes that the trend in the stabilization energies of these complexes $\text{CH}_3\text{F}\cdots\text{HONO}$, $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2\cdots\text{HONO}$ and $\text{CHF}_3\cdots\text{HONO}$ (-7.01 , -3.55 , -3.06 kcal mol $^{-1}$) in *cis* complexes and (-3.83 , -3.06 , -2.61 kcal mol $^{-1}$) in *trans* complexes correlate well with the optimized C-F bond lengths encountered in the fluoromethanes monomers (1.3781 Å, 1.3504 Å, 1.3168 Å (*cis*) and 1.3813 Å, 1.3547 Å, 1.3284 Å (*trans*)). The formation of the C-F...HONO hydrogen bond leads to a

significant elongation of C-F bond in all the complexes. Simultaneously all other C-F or C-H bonds in fluoro-methanes are contracted. The concise data of the above, are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparative data of alteration of bond lengths in atoms involved in H-bond complex between HONO and fluoro-methanes

	Free state (Å)	<i>cis</i> Complex (Å)	<i>trans</i> Complex (Å)
CH ₃ F			
$\nu(\text{C-H})$	1.0827	1.0807	1.0802
$\nu(\text{C-F})$	1.3647	1.3781	1.3813
$\nu(\text{F}\cdots\text{H})$	-	1.9439	1.9110
CH ₂ F ₂			
$\nu(\text{C-H})$	1.0800	1.0788	1.0781
$\nu(\text{C-F})$	1.3384, 1.3385	1.3504, 1.3342	1.3519, 1.3547
$\nu(\text{F}\cdots\text{H})$	-	2.0747	2.0423
CH ₃ F			
$\nu(\text{C-H})$	1.0767	1.0741	1.0756
$\nu(\text{C-F})$	1.3168	1.3135, 1.3309	1.3284, 1.3118
$\nu(\text{F}\cdots\text{H})$	-	2.1387	2.1482

Vibrational frequencies :

Computed vibrational frequencies of nitrous acid, fluoro-methanes, in monomeric forms, are shown in Tables 4-7. It can be seen from the results of nitrous acid (Table 4)

that calculated values are in good agreement with the experimental results especially, the bending modes. The calculated stretching frequencies deviate from the experiment because they are recorded in larger amount of monomers in gaseous phase.

The computed values of fluoro-methanes (Tables 5-7) are in close agreement with the experiment results. We can establish the fact that the computed values of their complexes shall also be in good agreement with the experiment if in future, some experimentalist scan the vibrational spectra.

Vibrational frequencies CH₃F...HONO complex :

The vibrational spectra of CH₃-F/HONO (*cis/trans*) complexes are shown in Tables 8 and 9. The $\nu_1(\text{O-H})$ stretch show red shift by 68 cm⁻¹ and 100 cm⁻¹ respectively for both *cis*- and *trans*-forms on complexation. Further, the $\nu(\text{F}\cdots\text{H})$ stretching frequencies occur at 150 cm⁻¹ and 171 cm⁻¹ for *cis* and *trans* complexes respectively. This observation correlates well with the lengthening of C-F, O-H and F...H bond lengths. While other stretching modes of $\nu(\text{N-O})$ show blue shift by 29 cm⁻¹ and 57 cm⁻¹ for *cis* and *trans* H-bonded respectively. This also correlates well with the shortening of N-O bond length by 0.0046 Å and 0.0122 Å for *cis* and *trans* com-

Table 4. Computed vibrational frequencies of HONO (*cis* and *trans*) at HF/6-31/G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2	Scaled values	Expt. ^a
<i>cis</i> -HONO				
$\nu_1(\text{O-H stretch})$	4008.8 (64) ^b	4010 (63)	3278 ^c	3412.4
$\nu_2(\text{N=O stretch})$	1985.5 (229)	1984 (229)	1622	1634.0
$\nu_3(\text{N-O-H bend})$	1524 (11)	1524 (11)	1246	-
$\nu_4(\text{N-O stretch})$	1164.8 (347)	1163 (346)	951	853.1
$\nu_5(\text{O-N-O bend})$	785 (16)	784 (16)	641	-
$\nu_6(\text{O-N-OH out-of-plane twist})$	741 (151)	740 (151)	605	638.4
<i>trans</i> -HONO				
$\nu_1(\text{O-H stretch})$	4148.9 (125)	4148.8 (125)	3580 ^d	3572.6
$\nu_2(\text{N=O stretch})$	2041 (156)	2040.7 (156)	1760	1689.1
$\nu_3(\text{N-O-H bend} + \text{N-O stretch})$	1495 (264)	1495.4 (265)	1290	1265.8
$\nu_4(\text{N=O stretch})$	1099.5 (227)	1099.3 (225)	948	800.4
$\nu_5(\text{O-N-O bend})$	792 (19)	793 (19.4)	684	796.6
$\nu_6(\text{O-N-OH twist})$	601 (136)	601 (135)	518	549.4

^aTaken from Ref. 42.

^bThe numbers in parantheses are the respective intensities in km/mol.

^cScale factor = $\nu_{\text{obs}}/\nu_{\text{cal}} = 0.8175$.

^dScale factor = 0.8629

Table 5. Computed vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) of CH_3F obtained from HF/6-31/G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2	Expt. ^a
$\nu_1(\text{C-H asym. stretch})$	3285 (58)	3284 (57)	3111.43
$\nu_2(\text{CH}_2 \text{ sym. stretch})$	3202 (32)	3201 (31)	3037.8
$\nu_3(\text{CH}_3 \text{ in-plane bending})$	1633 (1.4)	1632 (1.7)	1523.5
$\nu_4(\text{CH}_3 \text{ out-of-plane bending})$	1310 (3.0)	1311 (3.7)	1205.1
$\nu_5(\text{C-F stretch})$	1187 (126)	1186 (127)	1091.7

^aIR spectra of CH_3F in liquid solution, taken from Ref. 43. Numbers in parentheses are respective intensities in km/mol .

Table 6. Computed vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) of CH_2F_2 obtained from HF/6-31G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2	Expt. ^a
$\nu_1(\text{CH}_2 \text{ asym. stretch})$	3348 (67)	3347 (67)	3122.0
$\nu_2(\text{CH}_2 \text{ sym-stretch})$	3268.7 (51)	3267 (52)	3059.6
$\nu_3(\text{CH}_2 \text{ bending in-plane})$	1691 (7)	1691 (6.7)	1568
$\nu_4(\text{CH}_2 \text{ bending out-of-plane})$	1621 (51)	1620 (51)	1502
$\nu_5(\text{HCF bending out-of-plane})$	1397 (1)	1397 (1.2)	1276
$\nu_6(\text{HCF bending in-plane})$	1299 (30)	1298 (30)	1196
$\nu_7(\text{CF}_2 \text{ asym. stretch})$	1261 (197)	1260 (197)	1129
$\nu_8(\text{CF}_2 \text{ stretch})$	1255 (183)	1254 (182)	1128
$\nu_9(\text{CF}_2 \text{ bending})$	576 (6.8)	575 (6.7)	518

The number in parentheses are respective intensities in km/mol .

^aTaken from Ref. 42.

Table 7. Computed vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) of CHF_3 obtained from HF/6-31G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2	Expt. ^a
$\nu_1(\text{C-H stretch})$	3356 (56)	3355 (55)	3145.9
$\nu_2(\text{C-H wagging})$	1576 (108)	1577 (109)	1431.9
$\nu_3(\text{CF}_3 \text{ sym. stretch})$	1327 (272)	1325 (270)	1182.8
$\nu_4(\text{CF}_3 \text{ asym. stretch})$	1263 (144)	1260 (144)	1149.9
$\nu_5(\text{CF}_3 \text{ bending})$	764 (20)	760 (22)	694.3
$\nu_6(\text{CF wagging})$	553 (5)	550 (4.2)	496.8

The numbers in parentheses are respective intensities in km/mol .

^aTaken from Ref. 42.

Tables 8. Computed vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) of $\text{CH}_3\text{F}\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*cis*) complex at HF/6-31G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2
$\nu_1(\text{O-H stretch})$	3949 (301)	3942 (289)
$\nu_2(\text{CH}_3 \text{ asym. stretch})$	3315 (38)	3318 (40)
$\nu_3(\text{CH}_3 \text{ sym. stretch})$	3223 (28)	3202 (28)
$\nu_4(\text{N=O stretch})$	1977 (232)	1975 (230)
$\nu_5(\text{H-O-N in-plane bending})$	1548 (29)	1545 (27)
$\nu_6(\text{N-O stretch})$	1194 (321)	1192 (319)
$\nu_7(\text{C-F stretch})$	1143 (203)	1142 (201)
$\nu_8(\text{H-O-N stretch out-of-plane bending})$	858 (155)	855 (152)

Table 9. Computed vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) of $\text{CH}_3\text{F}\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*trans*) complex at HF/6-31G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2
$\nu_1(\text{O-H stretch})$	4081 (426)	4080 (422)
$\nu_2(\text{CH}_3 \text{ asym. stretch})$	3318 (36)	3317 (35)
$\nu_3(\text{CH}_3 \text{ sym. stretch})$	3227 (24)	3225 (22)
$\nu_4(\text{N=O stretch})$	2027 (174)	2027 (174)
$\nu_5(\text{HONO stretch})$	1564 (255)	1562 (251)
$\nu_6(\text{N-O stretch})$	1158 (252)	1156 (250)
$\nu_7(\text{C-F stretch})$	1125 (136)	1121 (130)
$\nu_8(\text{H-O-N bending})$	750 (126)	745 (122)
$\nu_9(\text{H}\cdots\text{F stretch})$	175 (10)	171 (9)

The numbers in parenthesis are respective intensities in km/mol .

plexation respectively. The magnitude of the decrease in the N-O bond length and increase in stretching frequencies are also in line with those previously reported results of $\text{XCHS}\cdots\text{HNO}$ complex⁴⁴.

$\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2\cdots\text{HONO}$ complex :

The spectra of $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*cis/trans*) complexes are given in Tables 10 and 11. The stretching frequency $\nu_1(\text{O-H})$ show red shift by 22 cm^{-1} and 37 cm^{-1} for *cis* and *trans* complexes respectively. The red shift in $\nu(\text{F}\cdots\text{H})$ stretching frequencies occur at 45 cm^{-1} and 65 cm^{-1} for *cis* and *trans* complexes respectively. These observations also correlate well with lengthening of C-F, O-H and $\text{F}\cdots\text{H}$ bond lengths, while other stretching modes of non-bonded $\nu(\text{N-O})$ show blue shifts by 17 cm^{-1} , 23 cm^{-1} for *cis* and *trans* complexes. These observations also correlate well with the shortening of N-O bond length by 0.0028 \AA and 0.0093 \AA in both complexes.

Table 10. Computed vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) of $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2\cdots\text{HONO}$ (*cis*) complex at HF/6-31G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2
$\nu_1(\text{O-H stretch})$	3989.7 (204)	3988 (202)
$\nu_2(\text{CH}_2 \text{ asym. stretch})$	3352 (51)	3350 (49)
$\nu_3(\text{CH}_2 \text{ sym. stretch})$	3273 (46)	3272 (46)
$\nu_4(\text{N=O stretch})$	1981 (227)	1979 (225)
$\nu_5(\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2 \text{ bending})$	1296 (29)	1295 (29)
$\nu_6(\text{C-F stretch})$	1258 (205)	1256 (201)
$\nu_7(\text{O-N-OH twist})$	1208 (155)	1201 (151)
$\nu_8(\text{N-O stretch})$	1182 (400)	1180 (402)
$\nu_9(\text{O-N-O in-plane bending})$	809.5 (147)	807 (141)

The numbers in parentheses are respective intensities in km/mol .

Table 11. Computed vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) of $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2 \cdots \text{HONO}$ (*trans*) complex at HF/6-31G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2
$\nu_1(\text{O-H stretch})$	4113 (361)	4111 (359)
$\nu_2(\text{CH}_2 \text{ asym. stretch})$	3358 (49)	3352 (40)
$\nu_3(\text{CH}_2 \text{ sym. stretch})$	3277 (46)	3275 (50)
$\nu_4(\text{N=O stretch})$	2027 (163)	2021 (159)
$\nu_5(\text{N-O-H out-of-plane})$	1533 (263)	1530 (261)
$\nu_6(\text{CH}_2\text{F wagging})$	1256 (180)	1255 (178)
$\nu_7(\text{C-F stretch})$	1202 (212)	1200 (210)
$\nu_8(\text{N-O stretch})$	1129 (265)	1122 (270)
$\nu_9(\text{HONO twist})$	702 (115)	700 (111)
$\nu_{10}(\text{CF}_2 \text{ bending})$	573.7 (μ)	570 (13)
$\nu_{11}(\text{H} \cdots \text{F stretch})$	66 (4.8)	65 (4.2)

The numbers in parentheses are respective intensities in km/mol .

$\text{CHF}_3 \cdots \text{HONO}$ complex :

The stretching and bending modes of vibrations are given in Tables 12 and 13. The stretching mode $\nu_1(\text{O-H})$ show red shift by 21 cm^{-1} and 8 cm^{-1} respectively for *cis* and *trans* complexes. The non-bonded $\nu(\text{N-O})$ stretch in both complexes show blue shift by 18 cm^{-1} and 28 cm^{-1} . This correlates well with the shortening of N-O bond lengths by 0.0084 \AA and 0.0047 \AA in both complexes respectively. The $\nu(\text{F} \cdots \text{H})$ stretching mode are computed to be 65 cm^{-1} and 103 cm^{-1} respectively for *cis* and *trans* complexes.

We can summarize the results in a way that the red shift is observed for those groups of atoms which are involved in complexation whereas blue shift occurs for non-bonded groups of atoms. The computed values of

Table 12. Computed vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) of $\text{CHF}_3 \cdots \text{HONO}$ (*cis*) complex at HF/6-31G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2
$\nu_1(\text{O-H stretch})$	3991 (166)	3989 (165)
$\nu_2(\text{C-F stretch})$	3399.7 (28)	3392 (28)
$\nu_3(\text{N=O stretch})$	1966 (239)	1965 (240)
$\nu_4(\text{C-F stretch})$	1336 (269)	1334 (269)
$\nu_5(\text{CF}_2 \text{ asym. stretch})$	1300 (326)	1298 (320)
$\nu_6(\text{N-O stretch})$	1194 (230)	1191 (229)
$\nu_7(\text{H-O-N wagging out-of-plane})$	791 (125)	790 (125)
$\nu_8(\text{CF}_3 \text{ out-of-plane of bending})$	756 (23)	756 (25)
$\nu_9(\text{CF}_3 \text{ in-plane of bending})$	545 (4.7)	540 (4.7)
$\nu_{10}(\text{H} \cdots \text{F stretch})$	66 (4.8)	65 (4.2)

The numbers in parentheses are respective intensities in km/mol .

Table 13. Computed vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) of $\text{CHF}_3 \cdots \text{HONO}$ (*trans*) complex at HF/6-31G** and MP2 levels

Mode	HF	MP2
$\nu_1(\text{O-H stretch})$	4142 (297)	4140 (290)
$\nu_2(\text{C-H stretch})$	3376 (44)	3371 (40)
$\nu_3(\text{N=O stretch})$	2033 (165)	2031 (166)
$\nu_4(\text{CH/OH bending})$	1577 (117)	1576 (120)
$\nu_5(\text{CF}_2 \text{ asym. stretch})$	1339 (263)	1335 (261)
$\nu_6(\text{CF}_2 \text{ sym. stretch})$	1304 (249)	1301 (250)
$\nu_7(\text{CF}_2 \text{ sym. stretch})$	1251 (201)	1249 (200)
$\nu_8(\text{N-O stretch})$	1119 (272)	1117 (270)
$\nu_9(\text{O-N-O in-plane bending})$	800 (8)	803 (7)
$\nu_{10}(\text{CF}_2 \text{ bending})$	761 (21)	760 (20)
$\nu_{11}(\text{H} \cdots \text{F stretch})$	104 (3)	103 (4)

The numbers in parentheses are respective intensities in km/mol .

red shifts and blue shifts show a decreasing trend as we go from CH_3F to CHF_3 system. This is consistent with the earlier experimental and theoretical calculations for other systems⁴⁵.

We further carried out the H-bonded complexation of another HONO (*trans*) monomer with $\text{CHF}_3 \cdots \text{HONO}$ complex at MP2/6-31G** level. We observed that HONO (*trans*) molecules do not undergo further H-bond making with other F-atoms in CHF_3 , but instead, they polymerize with one another and this continues. Another interesting observation, is that HONO (*cis*) monomers exist in tetra-form and looks like cyclobutane structure. This study is quite interesting from the point of view of atmospheric science which can help in understanding the mechanism of eradicating further depletion of ozone layer and help in protecting the green environment.

Conclusion :

The C-F \cdots H-O hydrogen bond on the $\text{HONO} \cdots \text{CH}_3\text{F}$, $\text{HONO} \cdots \text{CH}_2\text{F}_2$ and $\text{HONO} \cdots \text{CHF}_3$ systems have been studied including binding energy at MP2/6-31G** level. Our study indicates that the *cis*- HONO complexes with fluoro-methanes are predicted to be stronger than *trans*- HONO complexes. Further, there is shortening of the C-F (non-bonded) and lengthening of H-O bond (participating in H-bond) in both types of complexes. This observation correlates well with earlier studies and with blue-shifted vibrational frequencies of these bonds, in complexes. The calculated binding energies and electronic parameters for these systems indicate that these

kinds of hydrogen bonds can contribute to define the 3D structure of organic molecules and especially to define stable crystals. The experimental results in future, may be able to support the later idea that these forces are able to maintain the complex structure in solutions as it is found in gaseous phase.

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